

Generic Oral Hypoglycaemic Drugs of the Jan Aushadhi Scheme in India and their Branded Counterparts: A Cost Comparison Study

Somya Gupta¹, Surendra K. Bouddh², B.P. Kale³

¹Resident, Department of Pharmacology, Govt. Medical College, Datia (M.P)

²Professor and Head, Department of Pharmacology, Govt. Medical College, Datia (M.P)

³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Govt. Medical College, Datia (M.P)

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Surendra K. Bouddh

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: India grapples with a rising diabetes burden, prompting concern over treatment costs. The Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) aims to provide affordable generic medicines, particularly for underprivileged populations.

Aim: This study compares Jan Aushadhi generic antidiabetic drugs with branded counterparts to analyze cost discrepancies and their impact on treatment expenses.

Methods: Prices of Jan Aushadhi generics and branded drugs were compared, revealing substantial variations. Cost ratios and variations were computed, underscoring the need for informed decision-making.

Results: Over 70% of Jan Aushadhi generics were cheaper, though exceptions existed such as Sitagliptin tablets. Significant cost disparities were observed, with Canagliflozin showing the highest difference. Cost ratios ranged widely, emphasizing the importance of cost-conscious choices. Variations in costs highlighted the need for effective drug marketing management.

Conclusions: Selectively opting for Jan Aushadhi generics could alleviate medication costs in India, prompting a review of pricing policies. Price differences between generics and branded drugs underscore the necessity for better management. Increased awareness among stakeholders is crucial, and transitioning to PMBJP generics could enhance healthcare affordability.

Key Messages: While not all Jan Aushadhi generics are cheaper, a majority offer cost-saving benefit. Informed decisions can significantly reduce treatment expenses, emphasizing the importance of pharmacoeconomic considerations.

Keywords: Pharmacoeconomics, Jan Aushadi, Oral Hypoglycaemic Drugs, Cost Variance.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Diabetes stands as a major global health crisis in this century, securing its place among the top 10 causes of death, alongside cardiovascular disease (CVD), respiratory conditions, and cancer [1,2]. As per the World Health Organization (WHO), noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) were responsible for 74% of global deaths in 2019. Among them, diabetes led to 1.6 million fatalities, establishing itself as the ninth most prevalent cause of death worldwide [2]. By 2035, it is projected that approximately 592 million individuals may succumb to diabetes [3], thus an issue to be addressed.

India holds the position of being the second most affected country globally, following China, in terms of diabetes prevalence among individuals aged 20–79 years. In 2019, the count stood at 77 million, and projections suggest an increase to around 101 million by 2030 and 134.2 million by

2045 [4]. Diabetes imposes a substantial economic burden in India. The chronicity of disease and high costs of anti-diabetic drugs drain patients financially. The average annual direct costs of diabetes were INR 18,890, INR 10,585, INR 45,792, and INR 8,822 for the north, south, north-east, and west zones, respectively [5]. Rising healthcare costs are a global concern, particularly in underdeveloped and developing countries like India. Within this context, it is alarming that medicines constitute a significant portion of out-of-pocket healthcare spending in India, pushing many households into financial hardship.

A study from three north Indian states on burden of medicines showed that the reason for debt was medical expenditure in 25% of the urban households and 19% of rural households [6], which suggested that the poor were approaching lenders for borrowing money or selling their assets in order

to meet the healthcare expenses. In India, most patients who seek treatment for acute and chronic diseases face a major crisis for accessing essential medicines [7]. Several studies have shown that generic drugs are as effective as branded drugs and compliant with the Indian Pharmacopoeia standards for quality [8]. Additionally, comparative studies have also affirmed that substitution with generics can result in almost 15% savings on the medication cost [9]. In pharmaceutical research primary objective is to identify the most economical drug or combination, thereby mitigating the financial burden on both the patient and society [10].

Thus with an objective to Promote universal access to quality medicines, particularly for the underprivileged, and raise awareness about generic alternatives, the Indian government (Department of Pharmaceuticals, Ministry of Chemicals & Fertilizers), in November 2008 launched the Jan Aushadhi campaign. Under this scheme, dedicated outlets known as Janaushadhi Kendra's were opened to provide generic medicines.

This initiative aimed to provide high-quality generic medicines at more affordable prices compared to their branded counterparts through government-controlled centres.

As on 31.05.2023, 9484 Janaushadhi Kendra's are functional across the country. Product basket of PMBJP comprises 1800 drugs and 285 surgical equipment which are sold at retail shops at 50% to 90% cheaper than branded medicines [11].

In relation to the pharmaceuticals offered at Jan Aushadhi outlets, studies show significant cost differences for psychotropic medications, anticancer drugs utilized in breast cancer treatment, as well as anticoagulants, antiplatelets, and fibrinolytics employed for managing thromboembolic disorders when compared to their branded counterparts [10, 12, 13].

This study examines the pricing difference of generic hypoglycaemic medications found at Jan Aushadhi pharmacies in comparison to the most expensive and least expensive branded drugs, which share the same molecular composition and dosage and are available across the entire Indian market.

Material and Methods:

Study Area: Govt. Tertiary Care Institute Datia, (M.P.)

Study type: Comparative study

Study duration: Data collection and compilation is done within 1 month from the date of study approval.

Inclusion Criteria: Oral hypoglycaemic drugs listed in current master list of the Pradhan Mantri

Bharatiya Jan Aushadhi scheme brochure and from the Pharmaceuticals & Medical Devices Bureau of India (as of 2023)

Exclusion Criteria: Oral hypoglycaemic drugs not listed in current master list (as of 2023) of the Pradhan Mantri Bharatiya Jan Aushadhi scheme brochure.

Procedure: The assessment of pricing of Generic Anti-diabetic Drugs was carried out by referencing the current master list of the Pradhan Mantri Bharatiya Jan Aushadhi scheme brochure and gathering data from the Pharmaceuticals & Medical Devices Bureau of India [14]. Due to the wide array of companies producing or promoting generic drugs with similar compositions but varying costs, our methodology involved documenting the highest and lowest-cost formulations for each drug. The expenses linked to the most expensive and least expensive branded drugs were extracted from the Current Index of Medical Stores for our investigation [15]. Cost Difference (CD) [16]

In delineating the cost distinctions, we compared the cost of each drug with that of Jan Aushadhi. Specifically, the cost difference (CD) was calculated by subtracting the Jan Aushadhi cost from both the costliest and cheapest brand.

Cost Ratio (CR) [16]: The cost ratio was derived using the formula: maximum cost ÷ minimum cost. Cost variance (CV) [16].

Additionally, the coefficient of variation (CV) was determined as (maximum cost - minimum cost) x 100 ÷ minimum cost. All monetary values were denominated in Indian Rupees (INR) per unit, whether it is a tablet, capsule.

To present the findings on price disparities, we portrayed the actual cost per unit in INR. To uphold ethical standards and account for the fluidity of market prices, no disclosure was made regarding the names of the highest and lowest-cost formulations, along with details about their manufacturers. This measure safeguards the integrity of the study and mitigates potential concerns related to plagiarism.

This was an analytical study, conducted after obtaining Institutional Ethics Committee approval no.1217/Pharma/IECBMHR/GMC/2023.

Statistical Analysis: The data obtained from mentioned sources and were analyzed using Microsoft Excel software. The price variations have been expressed in percentage, cost ratio has been expressed in numbers, and results are shown in Table.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of difference in actual costs, cost ratio, and cost variance between the Jan Aushadhi generic drugs and expensive and inexpensive branded hypoglycaemic drugs marketed in India. "Costliest" refers to the costliest available branded drug and "Cheapest" refers to the cheapest available branded drug. JAS: Jan Aushadhi scheme, INR refers to Indian National Rupees)

Generic name of drug	Cost of single tablet in INR (Indian National rupees)			Difference in actual cost price in INR		Cost ratio(CR)		Cost variance(CV)	
	JAS price	Cheapest	Costliest	Cheapest	Costliest	Cheapest	Costliest	Cheapest	Costliest
glimipride 2mg	0.55	0.74	28.3	0.19	27.75	1.35	51.45	34.55	5045.45
glimipride 4mg	0.8	1.38	26	0.58	25.20	1.73	32.50	72.50	3150.00
metformin 1000mg	1.32	1.03	41.7	-0.29	40.38	0.78	31.59	-21.97	3059.09
glimipride 3mg	0.66	0.92	15.9	0.26	15.24	1.39	24.09	39.39	2309.09
voglibose 0.2mg	1.21	0.95	27.8	-0.26	26.59	0.79	22.98	-21.49	2197.52
vildagliptine 50mg and metformin 500mg	2.3	3.22	44.1	0.92	41.80	1.40	19.17	40.00	1817.39
voglibose 0.3mg	1.54	1.38	27.1	-0.16	25.56	0.90	17.60	-10.39	1659.74
glipizide 5mg and metformin 500mg	0.9	0.67	15.2	-0.23	14.30	0.74	16.89	-25.56	1588.89
vildagliptine 50 mg	2.33	3.04	32.1	0.71	29.77	1.30	13.78	30.47	1277.68
pioglitazone 30mg	1.32	1.38	17.5	0.06	16.18	1.05	13.26	4.55	1225.76
dapagliflozin 5mg	2.5	2.67	31.64	0.17	29.14	1.07	12.66	6.80	1165.60
dapagliflozin 10mg and metformin 500mg	5.1	10.7	64.14	5.60	59.04	2.10	12.58	109.80	1157.65
dapagliflozin 10mg and metformin 1000mg	5.5	8.3	66.43	2.80	60.93	1.51	12.08	50.91	1107.82
metformin 500mg and voglibose 0.3mg	1.65	2.76	18.3	1.11	16.65	1.67	11.09	67.27	1009.09
dapagliflozin 10mg	3.2	4.14	33.36	0.94	30.16	1.29	10.43	29.38	942.50
metformin 500mg and voglibose 0.2mg	1.54	2.23	14.2	0.69	12.66	1.45	9.22	44.81	822.08
glimipride 1mg	0.4	0.46	3.48	0.06	3.08	1.15	8.70	15.00	770.00
vildagliptine 100mg	4.5	6.06	39.14	1.56	34.64	1.35	8.70	34.67	769.78
vildagliptine 50mg and metformin 850mg	3	4.6	25.53	1.60	22.53	1.53	8.51	53.33	751.00
gliclazide 80mg	2.4	0.32	20.29	-2.08	17.89	0.13	8.45	-86.67	745.42
metformin 500mg and voglibose.3mg and glimipride 1mg	2.5	4.42	20.33	1.92	17.83	1.77	8.13	76.80	713.20
metformin 500mg and voglibose.2mg and glimipride 2mg	3.19	3.5	25.3	0.31	22.11	1.10	7.93	9.72	693.10
metformin 500mg	1.76	2.5	13.7	0.74	11.94	1.42	7.78	42.05	678.41

andglimipride 1mg									
metformin 1000mg andglimipride 3mg	2.9	1.14	22.3	-1.76	19.40	0.39	7.69	-60.69	668.97
glibenclamide 5mg andmetformin 500mg	1.2	5.4	9.16	4.20	7.96	4.50	7.63	350.00	663.33
repaglinide 2mg and metformin 500mg	3.5	2.5	26.4	-1.00	22.90	0.71	7.54	-28.57	654.29
metformin 500mg and voglibose.3mg and glimipride 2mg	3	4.78	22.47	1.78	19.47	1.59	7.49	59.33	649.00
repaglinide 1mg	2.5	0.92	18	-1.58	15.50	0.37	7.20	-63.20	620.00
glimipride 2mg and metformin 500mg pioglitazone 15mg	2.42	9.11	17.3	6.69	14.88	3.76	7.15	276.45	614.88
linagliptine 5mg	4.5	8.28	31.9	3.78	27.40	1.84	7.09	84.00	608.89
metformin 500mg andglimipride 2mg	2.64	2.7	18.7	0.06	16.06	1.02	7.08	2.27	608.33
repaglinide 1mg and metformin 500mg	3	10.6	21	7.60	18.00	3.53	7.00	253.33	600.00
sitagliptine 50mg and metformin 500mg	5.5	5.5	38.3	0.00	32.80	1.00	6.96	0.00	596.36
repaglinide 2mg	3.5	7.36	23.4	3.86	19.90	2.10	6.69	110.29	568.57
tenegliptine 20mg andmetformin 500mg	3	5	19.6	2.00	16.60	1.67	6.53	66.67	553.33
metformin 500mg and voglibose.2mg and glimipride 1mg	3	2.5	19.13	-0.50	16.13	0.83	6.38	-16.67	537.67
sitagliptine 50mg	6	3.22	38.14	-2.78	32.14	0.54	6.36	-46.33	535.67

repaglinide 0.5mg	1.5	2.02	9.4	0.52	7.90	1.35	6.27	34.67	526.67
metformin 1000mg andglimipride 1mg	2.86	2.6	16.2	-0.26	13.34	0.91	5.66	-9.09	466.43
metformin 850mg and glimipride 3mg	2.5	10.6	14.1	8.10	11.60	4.24	5.64	324.00	464.00
vildagliptine 50mg and metformin 1000mg	3.3	12.6	18.6	9.30	15.30	3.82	5.64	281.82	463.64
metformin 1000mg andglimipride 4mg	3.06	5.7	16.5	2.64	13.44	1.86	5.39	86.27	439.22
metformin 1000mg and voglibose.3mg and glimipride 2mg	3.6	16.13	19	12.53	15.40	4.48	5.28	348.06	427.78
linagliptine 2.5mg andmetformin 500mg	3.5	8.28	17.9	4.78	14.40	2.37	5.11	136.57	411.43
metformin 850mg	1.98	0.66	10.1	-1.32	8.12	0.33	5.10	-66.67	410.10
metformin 1000mg andglimipride 2mg	3.63	2.53	18.4	-1.10	14.77	0.70	5.07	-30.30	406.89
teneligliptine 20mg	2	2.2	9.94	0.20	7.94	1.10	4.97	10.00	397.00
gliclazide 60mg and metformin 500mg	3	4.78	14.7	1.78	11.70	1.59	4.90	59.33	390.00
tenegliptine 20mg and metformin 1000mg	4	6.37	19.33	2.37	15.33	1.59	4.83	59.25	383.25
gliclazide 40mg	1.54	0.84	7.36	-0.70	5.82	0.55	4.78	-45.45	377.92
linagliptine 2.5mg and metformin 1000mg	3.9	8.74	18.6	4.84	14.70	2.24	4.77	124.10	376.92
pioglitazone 15mg andmetformin 500mg	2.7	3.2	12.8	0.50	10.10	1.19	4.74	18.52	374.07
sitagliptine 100mg	10	6.5	42.7	-3.50	32.70	0.65	4.27	-35.00	327.00

pioglitazone 15mg	0.88	0.92	3.52	0.04	2.64	1.05	4.00	4.55	300.00
glibenclamide 5mg and metformin 500mg	2.75	4.55	10.1	1.80	7.35	1.65	3.67	65.45	267.27
pioglitazone 15mg									
gliclazide 80mg and metformin 500mg	2.86	6.8	9.72	3.94	6.86	2.38	3.40	137.76	239.86
glipizide 5mg	0.5	0.31	1.68	-0.19	1.18	0.62	3.36	-38.00	236.00
acarbose 25mg	4	3	13.4	-1.00	9.40	0.75	3.35	-25.00	235.00
canagliflozin 100mg	18.6	59	61.3	40.40	42.70	3.17	3.30	217.20	229.57

metformin 500mg and glimepiride 0.5mg	1.76	4.8	5.8	3.04	4.04	2.73	3.30	172.73	229.55
metformin 500mg	0.66	0.39	2.06	-0.27	1.40	0.59	3.12	-40.91	212.12
sitagliptin 50mg and metformin 1000mg	7	6.4	21.33	-0.60	14.33	0.91	3.05	-8.57	204.71
acarbose 50mg	6.2	2.93	18.8	-3.27	12.60	0.47	3.03	-52.74	203.23
gliclazide 60mg	4.4	11.5	12.2	7.10	7.80	2.61	2.77	161.36	177.27
acarbose 50mg and metformin 500mg	8.3	15.2	17.3	6.90	9.00	1.83	2.08	83.13	108.43
sitagliptin 100mg and metformin 1000mg	8.6	11.93	15.6	3.33	7.00	1.39	1.81	38.72	81.40

Cost Comparisons: Majority of Jan Aushadhi Drugs are Economical: Over 70% of Jan Aushadhi generic drugs are priced lower than their branded counterparts. Some drugs among cheapest branded was more affordable than the Jan Aushadhi generic counterpart. For instance, Sitagliptin 100mg cost INR 6.50 per tablet, whereas the Jan Aushadhi alternative was priced at INR 10.00 per tablet. In contrast, all other branded drugs exceeded the cost of Jan Aushadhi generics for all tablets.

Cost Differences (CD): Canagliflozin 100mg tablets showed the largest cost difference of 40.40 INR/tablet (cheapest branded priced at INR 59/tablet, Jan Aushadhi is priced at INR 18.6/tablet). On the other hand, the smallest difference was seen in a combination tablet of Sitagliptin and Metformin (50+500mg). In FDC (Fixed drug combination) highest cost difference was noted with dapagliflozin and metformin (10+1000mg) of 60.93 INR/tablet compared to expensive branded. Significantly, 70% of drugs demonstrate a positive cost difference between branded and Jan Aushadhi generics, indicating a substantial monetary gap. Opting for Jan Aushadhi generics can result in considerable cost savings.

Cost Ratio (CR) Analysis: Cost ratios vary widely, ranging from 1.81 to 51.45 compared to the costliest branded drugs and from 0.13 to 4.50 compared to the cheapest. This broad range underscores the importance of making judicious choices to achieve more substantial cost savings.

In comparison to the costliest brand, CR ranged from 1.81 to 51.45, with Glimipiride 2mg having the highest and FDC (Fixed drug combination) of Sitagliptin and Metformin (100mg+ 1000mg) have the lowest ratio. When generic of JAS (Jan

Aushadhi Scheme) compared to the cheapest branded, CR ranged from 0.13 to 4.50, with Glibenclamide and Metformin (5mg+ 500mg) having the highest and Gliclazide 80mg is having the lowest.

Cost of Variance (CV) Analysis: Jan Aushadhi generic drugs displayed a CV ranging from 5045.45 (Glimipiride 2mg) to 81.40

{Sitagliptin and Metformin (100mg +1000mg)} when compared to the costliest branded drugs. In comparison to the cheapest branded drugs, the CV varied from 350 (Glibenclamide 5mg and Metformin 500mg) followed by Glimipiride and Metformin fixed dose combination and least seen with -86.67 (Gliclazide 80mg).

Smart Medication Selection for Cost Savings: Given the diverse cost ratios, significant cost differences and wide range of cost variance making informed choices during medication selection can lead to more significant cost savings. This emphasizes the importance of choosing wisely among Jan Aushadhi generics for potential financial benefits.

Discussion

The assessment of the economic and social impact of diabetes in India is important for several reasons. First, India is considered the diabetes capital of the world, yet not enough is done to tackle the disease [17].

Our study shows that Jan Aushadhi's offer over 70% of its generic oral hypoglycaemic drugs at prices significantly below their branded counterparts. This affordability is achieved through the ingenious pricing strategy of the PMBJP,

setting medication costs at a mere half of the average price of the top three branded medicines. This not only ensures economic accessibility but also reflects a commitment to making essential medications available to a broader audience.

As per Shyam S, Mahanthegowda study Oral anti-diabetic drugs (OADs) are essential for the lifelong management of Type II Diabetes Mellitus, particularly in developing nations like India. The cost of these medications significantly influences healthcare management and patient adherence to the treatment plan, alongside considerations of safety and effectiveness their study results were similar with results of our study in single drug therapy and are in contrast with FDC. The results reported that glimepiride showed highest variation. Among FDC, greater difference found between glimepiride 2 mg and Metformin and least with Pioglitazone 7.5 mg and Metformin 500 mg (8%) [18] in contrast to our study which shows max variance with FDC of glibenclamide and metformin.

Study by Veena DR, Jagadish S et.al noted significant cost variations were observed among sulfonylurea drugs, with Glimepiride 1 mg tablet displaying the highest percentage increase (1366%). Meanwhile, in the nonsulfonylurea group, Metformin 500 mg tablet exhibited the greatest percentage variation (809%). Among fixed dose combinations (FDC) in combination therapy, Pioglitazone + Metformin (15 + 500) tablet showed the highest cost variation (166%). In single drug therapy the cost ratio ranged from 1.36 for Glibenclamide 5 mg to 14.65 for Glimepiride 1 mg among sulfonylurea group whereas minimum cost variation was observed for Pioglitazone + Glimepiride (15 + 2) tablet 5% at cost ratio of 1.05 [19] Similarly our study revealed significant cost disparities among various branded drugs utilized for Diabetes Mellitus (DM) in India. Another price variation analysis by Thacker et al.[20] also reported there was highest percentage of cost variation observed for glimepiride (1365%).

Our study results are in contrast with Gedam and Barmaiya [21], cost variation analysis of oral anti-diabetics available in Indian market. The results showed that highest variation of cost price was observed for Metformin 500 mg tablet (334%) followed by Glimepiride (162%). Based on the analysis of our study, there is evidence of differences in cost ratio and percentage of cost variation among all generic OADs (oral anti diabetic drugs), and there is an urgent need to address these variations by physicians while prescribing. Due to the long term treatment duration, diabetes patients usually have higher than average monthly out-of-pocket expenses and high out-of-pocket expenses can be a barrier to adherence to prescription drug regimens. Many

chronically ill adults cut back on medications due to high prescription cost. Inadequate prescription coverage and out of pocket expenses is one of the strongest predictors of their medication adherence problems order [22]. Hence it is desired that the Government should bring all lifesaving and essential medicines under price control. A drug audit suggests that, in India, almost 80% of all drugs are marketed as branded molecules and are more expensive than their unbranded generic counterparts [23] which also justifies our study finding. Also several studies have shown that generic drugs are as effective as branded drugs and compliant with the Indian Pharmacopoeia standards for quality [8]. Additionally, comparative studies have also affirmed that substitution with generics can result in almost 15% savings on the medication cost [9]. When considering the total healthcare expenditure, the cost of medicines and pharmaceutical products forms a major part, and deliberate attempts are being made at reducing the burden to the patient [24,25]. In this regard, reports from Europe and developing countries have shown that generic drugs can reduce the medicine bill substantially [9]. The key observation of this study is that the cost of Jan Aushadhi generic drugs were significantly less in the case of the most commonly used oral hypoglycaemic drugs. But the first line antidiabetic drug i.e. metformin available at Jan aushadhi Kendra is slightly more expensive i.e. by just 0.2-0.3 INR/tablet compared to cheapest branded alternatives.

Our research reveals notable price differences in medications within the Jan Aushadhi Scheme (JAS), particularly for widely-used oral hypoglycaemic drugs like glimepiride, where JAS offers lower prices than the cheapest branded alternatives. However, we also identify more affordable branded options, especially in the biguanide and alpha-glucosidase inhibitor drug category, where their prices are lower than JAS. Many studies have compared prices of Jan Aushadhi medicines with available branded/generic medicines focusing on other therapeutic areas, studies have shown that providing a manual of comparative drug prices annotated with prescribing advice to physicians reduced their patients' drug expense [20]

Conclusion

Our findings suggest that the currently 70% of oral antidiabetics drug under JAS may effectively reduce out-of-pocket expenses for medicines in India and for rest 30% we strongly recommend a thorough re-evaluation of the medicine pricing policy under JAS by the Government of India as this may raise concerns about the effectiveness of JAS in achieving its goals. The considerable percentage price variation among generic and branded drugs in India emphasizes the necessity to manage drug

marketing to maximize therapeutic benefits and minimize personal and economic consequences. Our study underscores the urgent need for heightened awareness among healthcare professionals, patients, and the public regarding medicine cost differences. Shifting to generic drugs, particularly those from the Pradhan Mantri Bhartiya Janaushadhi Pariyojana (PMBJP) has the potential to alleviate economic burdens by reducing treatment cost and enhance the overall healthcare system.

References

1. Cho NH, Shaw JE, Karuranga S, Huang Y, da Rocha Fernandes JD, Ohlrogge AW, Malanda B. IDF Diabetes Atlas: Global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2017 and projections for 2045. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2018 Apr; 138:271-281. doi: 10.1016/j.diabres.2018.02.023. Epub 2018 Feb 26. PMID: 29496507.
2. National center for health statistics, the top 10 causes of death. [Last accessed on October 2023]. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/nchs/fastats/leading-causes-of-death.htm>
3. Tao Z, Shi A, Zhao J. Epidemiological Perspectives of Diabetes. *Cell Biochem Biophys.* 2015 Sep; 73(1):181-5. doi: 10.1007/s12013-015-0598-4. PMID: 25711186.
4. Saeedi P, Petersohn I, Salpea P, Malanda B, Karuranga S, Unwin N, Colagiuri S, Guariguata L, Motala AA, Ogurtsova K, Shaw JE, Bright D, Williams R; IDF Diabetes Atlas Committee. Global and regional diabetes prevalence estimates for 2019 and projections for 2030 and 2045: Results from the International Diabetes Federation Diabetes Atlas, 9th edition. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2019 Nov; 157:107843. doi: 10.1016/j.diabres.2019.107843. Epub 2019 Sep 10. PMID: 31518657.
5. Oberoi S, Kansra P. Economic menace of diabetes in India: a systematic review. *Int J Diabetes Dev Ctries.* 2020 Oct; 40(4):464-475. doi: 10.1007/s13410-020-00838-z. Epub 2020 Jun 17. PMID: 32837090; PMCID: PMC7299136.
6. Mukherjee, K. A Cost Analysis of the Jan Aushadhi Scheme in India. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, 2017; 6(5): 253-256. doi: 10.15171/ijhpm.2017.02.
7. Bhargava A, Kalantri SP. The crisis in access to essential medicines in India: key issues which call for action. *Indian J Med Ethics.* 2013 Apr-Jun; 10(2):86-95. doi: 10.20529/IJME.2013.028. PMID: 23697486.
8. Joshi SS, Shetty YC, Karande S. Generic drugs - The Indian scenario. *J Postgrad Med.* 2019 Apr-Jun; 65(2):67-69. doi: 10.4103/jpgm.JPGM.420.18. PMID: 31036775; PMCID: PMC6515776.
9. Cameron A, Mantel-Teeuwisse AK, Leufkens HG, Laing RO. Switching from originator brand medicines to generic equivalents in selected developing countries: how much could be saved? *Value Health.* 2012 Jul-Aug; 15(5):664-73. doi: 10.1016/j.jval.2012.04.004. Epub 2012 Jul 11. PMID: 22867775.
10. Kashyap A, Balaji MN, Chhabra M, Rashid M, Muragundi PM. Cost analysis of various branded versus generic chemotherapeutic agents used for the treatment of early breast cancer- a deep insight from India. *Expert Rev Pharmacoecon Outcomes Res.* 2020 Aug; 20(4):355-361. doi: 10.1080/14737167.2019.1637735. Epub 2019 Jul 5. PMID: 31248303.
11. Aushadhi J. Government of India, BPPI. Available from: <http://www.janaushadhi.gov.in>.
12. Ice L. Nur, Neily Zakiyah, Lina Budiyantri, Auliya A. Suwantika. Cost-effectiveness analysis of psychotropic therapy in adolescent patients with intellectual disability in Mental Hospital of West Java Provincial State 2015-2017. *J Adv Pharm Edu Res.* 2019; 9(1):57-63.
13. Ray A, Najmi A, Khandelwal G, Sadasivam B. A Cost Variation Analysis of Drugs Available in the Indian Market for the Management of Thromboembolic Disorders. *Cureus.* 2020 May 5; 12(5):e7964. doi: 10.7759/cureus.7964. PMID: 32523821; PMCID: PMC7273361.
14. Pharmaceuticals & Medical Devices Bureau of India (PMBI): PMBJP products. Accessed: October, 2023: <http://janaushadhi.Gov.in/ProductList.aspx>,
15. CIMS: Search drug information, images & medical news. 2023. Accessed: October, 2023: <https://www.mims.com/india>
16. George T, Baliga M S. Generic Anticancer Drugs of the Jan Aushadhi Scheme in India and Their Branded Counterparts: The First Cost Comparison Study. *Cureus.* November 03, 2021; 13(11): e19231. doi:10.7759/cureus.19231
17. Guariguata L, Whiting DR, Hambleton I, Beagley J, Linnenkamp U, Shaw JE. Global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2013 and projections for 2035. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2014 Feb; 103(2):137-49. doi: 10.1016/j.diabres.2013.11.002. Epub 2013 Dec 1. PMID: 24630390.
18. Shyam S, Mahanthegowda BD. A cost variation analysis of various brands of oral anti-diabetic drugs currently available in Indian pharmaceutical market. *Int J Basic Clin Pharmacol [Internet].* 2020 Jul. 21 [cited 2024 Feb. 27]; 9(8):1253-7. Available from: <https://www.ijbcp.com/index.php/ijbcp/article/view/4193>
19. Veena DR, Jagadish S, Priya GC, Sareetha AV, Shanmukananda P. Cost variation analysis of oral anti-diabetic drugs available in Indian

- market. *Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol* 2023; 13(04):758-762.
20. S thacker k, r mistry v, j kanani n. Oral antidiabetics agents available in indian pharmaceutical market: a price variation analysis. *Asian j pharm clin res* [internet]. 2020 mar.7 [cited 2024feb.27];13(3):143-7. Available from: <https://journals.innovareacademics.in/index.php/ajpcr/article/view/36498>
 21. Gedam S, Barmaiya N. Cost variation analysis of oral anti-diabetic agents available in Indian market. *Int J Basic Clin Pharmacol* [Internet]. 2021 May 25 [cited 2024 Feb. 27]; 10(6):694-8. Available from: <https://www.ijbcp.com/index.php/ijbcp/article/view/4691>
 22. Acharya KG, Shah KN, Solanki ND, Rana DA. Evaluation of antidiabetic prescriptions, cost and adherence to treatment guidelines: A prospective, cross-sectional study at a tertiary care teaching hospital. *J Basic Clin Pharm.* 2013 Sep; 4(4):82-7. doi: 10.4103/0976-0105.121653. PMID: 24808678; PMCID: PMC3979268.
 23. Singal GL, Nanda A, Kotwani A. A comparative evaluation of price and quality of some branded versus branded-generic medicines of the same manufacturer in India. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2011 Apr; 43(2):131-6. doi: 10.4103/0253-7613.77344. PMID: 21572645; PMCID: PMC3081449.
 24. Wani MA, Tabish SA, Jan FA, Khan NA, Wafai ZA, Pandita KK. Cost analysis of inpatient cancer chemotherapy at a tertiary care hospital. *J Cancer Res Ther.* 2013 Jul- Sep; 9(3):397-401. doi: 10.4103/0973-1482.119314. PMID: 24125973.
 25. Mukherjee K. A Cost Analysis of the Jan Aushadhi Scheme in India. *Int J Health Policy Manag.* 2017 May 1; 6(5):253-256. doi: 10.15171/ijhpm.2017.02. PMID: 28812812; PMCID: PMC5417146.